

Green Software Development Model

An Approach towards Sustainable Software development

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Abstract—the Software development lifecycle (SDLC) currently focuses on systematic execution and maintenance of software by dividing the software development process into various phases that include requirements-gathering, design, implementation, testing, deployment and maintenance. The problem here is that certain important decisions taken in these phases like use of paper, generation of e-Waste, power consumption and increased carbon foot print by means of travel, Air-conditioning etc may harm the environment directly or indirectly. There is a dearth of models that define how a software can be developed and maintained in an environment friendly way. This paper discusses the changes in the existing SDLC and suggests appropriate steps which can lead to lower carbon emissions, power and paper use, thus helping organizations to move towards greener and sustainable software development.

I. INTRODUCTION

The paper here tries to explore if software can be developed in an environment friendly way by improving the process of software development. This paper focuses on some practices that can be incorporated to take environment friendly decisions for the software and its development process

In the past, environment friendly software development has got little attention. One such initiative is, The Green Project Management [1], which focuses on project management aspects in an environment friendly way. However, individual phases of software development lifecycle can benefit from environment friendly measures. On the other hand, a lot of research has gone into evaluate different factors such as power consumption by computers, monitors etc.

The whitepaper, Review of Computer Energy Consumption and Potential Savings [2], analyses the power consumption by computers and monitors in the recent years manufactured by different vendors. The Analysis was made for all the power states Active, low power and off states. The outcome was that computers and monitors consumed significant amount of power. TABLE I compares the power consumption of computers of different types that include desktops from various vendors manufactured during 1999-2001.

Description	Power Consumption of Computers in Watts (W)		
	Active	Low-power	Off
Desktop	55	25	1.5
Desktop with Power Management	36	27	-
Desktop without Power Management	48	-	-
Desktops manufactured 2000-2001	70	9	3
Desktop with pentium and Pre-pentium manufactured 1999	55	25	0
Desktop with -Macintosh manufacture in 1999	50	48	0

TABLE I - Power consumption of computers manufactured between 1999 and 2001 [2].

This is illustrated by the bar chart in Fig. 1, which is a plot of the data from TABLE I. The chart clearly shows that the power consumption of computers is steadily increasing with new hardware.

Fig. 1 - Power consumed by computers manufactured between 1999 and 2001 [2].

TABLE II shows the power consumption of computer monitors of different types. These include monitors of varied types CRT (cathode Ray tube) and LCD (liquid crystal display). These are of sizes between 15 to 17 inches.

Description	Power Consumption of Monitors in Watts (W)		
	Active	Low-power	Off
CRT with Power Management	66	15	-
CRT without Power Management	67	-	-
CRT	85	5	0.5
CRT 15"	75	10	0
CRT 17"	80	0-15	0
LCD	15	1.5	0.5
LCD 15"	30	2	2
LCD 17"	35	0-15	0.5

TABLE II - Power consumption of Monitors of different types [2].

The bar chart in Fig. 2 is a plot of the power consumed by different kinds of the monitors from TABLE II. Clearly LCD monitors consume much less power when compared to CRT. This also indicates that a significant amount of power can be saved if monitors are switched off when not in use.

Fig. 2 - Bar-chart Power consumption of computers manufactured between 1999 and 2001 [2].

Research studies have also shown that programming ways and use of programming constructs also impact the power consumption. The paper, Energy Estimation of Nested Loop Programs [3], discusses the impact of programming using loops and conditionals on power consumption. One of the research papers, The Effect of Compiler Optimizations on Pentium 4

Power Consumption [4], shows that code optimization manually or through compilers can reduce the power consumption of the processors. An online publication, India: A dumping ground for e-Waste [5] has shown that very large amount of e-Waste is generated every year. All these studies and facts analyzed in the past emphasizes the need to include some important practices that help in developing and maintaining the software system in an environment friendly way.

This paper depicts certain circumstances or decisions made in software development and maintenance phases which can impact the environmental conditions. It also suggests some improvements in the key software development phases to minimize the harmful effect on the environment. The same principles could be applied for software maintenance projects too.

II. EXPLANATION

The Green Software Development Model tries to refine the different phase of Software development by introducing a set of suggestions that can be followed in each of the phases namely requirement gathering, design, Implementation, testing, deployment, maintenance and retirement.

A. Requirement-Gathering

In the Requirement-Gathering phase, it is necessary to consider the shelf life of the software. The shelf life is period during which the software serves the society to achieve a particular goal. If the shelf-life is defined for a project, it would help to gather the requirement in both current and future perspective. On the other hand, it would help to develop the software in such a way that it could run on legacy hardware, as well as newer ones. This avoids disposal of existing hardware.

Capturing User Interface requirements also form an important part of the Requirement gathering. The emphasis should be on designing screens which do not use bright colors or colors that harm the eye of the user. Bright colors usually consume more power on the screen so could be avoided to a certain extent. Additionally, the requirement gathering process should also include switching off the devices, monitors or operating in low power mode when not in use. This will help reduce unnecessary power consumption by the system.

Throw away prototyping [6] should be avoided to elicit and understand the requirements. This is because the prototypes are just designed to understand the requirements and disposed there-after. This cannot be considered a good approach because significant amount power, paper and some custom hardware is used for the purpose. It may be recommended to develop a re-usable prototype, which can be used in future.

B. Design

In the Design phase, the primary goal should be to achieve simplicity in design. The design of the system should be made as simple as possible. The stakeholder should be able to understand

the design easily without much explanation. This leads to less paper work. Complex designs may lead to re-design and higher documentation effort using computers and devices which may lead to higher power consumption, fuel consumption on account of travel and other resource usage. If the design is complex, effort should be made to modularize it to reduce the complexity.

Re-use is another important factor for a design to be sustainable. Re-useable design can avoid re-implementation of components that are already available. Bringing in extensibility can be another way of bringing in re-usability, plug-in architecture [7] is popularly used to achieve both re-usability and extensibility with the software systems. These kinds of approaches should be used in the design phase, because they help in building a design which may undergo very minor changes in whole lifetime. Repetitive change in design can prove expensive in terms of effort and resources used in all other phases of SDLC. A design which always changes may not be considered environment friendly. A change in design may lead to a lot of paper work, use of tools to build or change of the design, impact both old and new hardware and software, higher consumption of power etc.

C. Implementation

The implementation phase is an important phase where the requirements and design are mapped together to build a working system. In the implementation phase, the first step usually aims at following the best practices of the organization's software development process. This enhances the quality of the software; however Sustainable or environment friendly implementation should also be another important goal.

For sustainable software implementation use of Application Programming Interface (API's) that are hardware-specific should be discouraged. This is because the software implementation is coupled to a particular kind of hardware. The disadvantage here is that if the hardware is obsolete the software becomes useless. An alternate approach would be to encourage building a hardware abstraction layer which decouples the software system from the hardware related complexities. Resource intensive API's and programming constructs like use of Mutex for synchronization of threads within a process, retaining a database connection for a long duration, use of nested loops, maintaining redundant copies of data etc should also avoided. These API's tend to consume additional resources in terms of hardware, memory, disk space, processor cycles etc. This makes the software non-functional and non-scalable with existing resources or legacy hardware. An approach to avoid such situation could be to profile the resource consuming API's and use them judiciously.

Automation of repetitive implementation tasks can be considered as very important part of sustainable implementation because they reduce the time taken to achieve the tasks and avoid manual errors as far as possible. Automated tools include automatic code generation tools, Automatic Code review tools, etc.

Pair-Programming [8] can also be enforced so as to reduce the number of resources in terms of computers or any other resource that needs to be used. These approaches can lead to better understanding and improved implementation of the software.

D. Testing

In the testing phase, a software system is verified and validated for its correctness. Unit tests play a major role in achieving defect free software at a more granular level. Lesser the defects, lesser the change required in the software.

Test Automation should be encouraged as they reduce manual errors. They also emphasize on re-use of test cases and standardize the testing process. This not only improves the accuracy of testing but also the productivity and reduces power consumed by additional resources in the manual testing process.

Performance Testing and resource profiling should also be promoted as a mandatory step in the testing process. Without these, there may be additional demand on hardware, processor cycles and memory. It may not be able function correctly with current or legacy systems which are of lower or moderate capacity in terms of hardware resources.

E. Deployment or Installation

In the deployment phase the actual software is prepared for being installed in the production environment. The size of the installation package plays a major role, larger the size of installation, more the time taken for installation in the production environment. This also adds an overhead of storage and maintenance and demands lot of disk space for storage. The size of deployment or installation packages should be minimized by using standard data compression techniques.

Use of CD(Compact Disc)s and DVD(Digital Versatile Disc)s or any other kind of disposable media form a major source of e-Waste as they are configured to be used on parameters such as definite number of installations, serial key based installation, machine or system based installation. An alternate approach could be the use of online license verification based installation to avoid the e-Waste created by disposable media significantly.

Standalone Installation could also be avoided as they can consume a lot of disk space. Modern ways of re-use for software installation can also be employed where a single copy of a software is deployed centrally and users can access it only when need arises.

F. Maintenance

A software system moves to maintenance phase when most of the features are implemented and at the same time the software is functioning well in the production environment for some time. This phase mainly includes fixing the bugs, fine-tuning the system, implementing new features, etc.

This phase bears the impact of all the other phases of software development. Documentation plays an important role in software maintenance. Documentation should be in electronic format to avoid the use of paper. Most of the times, quality of the software deteriorates in the maintenance phase. This is because the bugs are fixed without understanding the scenarios completely. There are some scenarios where temporary fixes are applied, which results in re-work and introduction of new problems with the software system. Problems generally include non-reproducible bugs and resource leaks or unnecessary resource demands on hardware, processor, memory etc when new features are to be implemented in the existing system; the quality of code is compromised. Such practices make the maintenance phase unsustainable or unfriendly to the environment.

Practices such as software archeology and software disassembling to understand or reproduce the software system could also be considered a bad practice, as it involves a lot of time, resources and power. This may also lead to implementation defects or problems due to lack of understanding. An alternate approach is to always ensure that a part of development team members themselves are involved in the maintenance phase. They always have a clear understanding of the system.

Software System migration should be avoided as much as possible as migration leads to disposal of legacy hardware, devices and also disposal of old technology. The system instead should be built in such a way that it is adaptable to the technologies used in the future and also the new devices and hardware capabilities. Organizations should prefer technologies that are platform and domain agnostic to avoid such problems. This will help avoid disposal of e-Waste such as legacy hardware or any other activity that affects the environment [9].

Additionally the maintenance phase involves the same phases of SDLC internally. Thus it is necessary follow the guidelines mentioned above for each of the phases to achieve sustainability in the maintenance phase

G. Retirement

Retirement is the last phase of the software system. This phase occurs when the lifetime of the software system ends. In the retirement phase, the reusable parts of the software should be archived for future use rather than disposing. All the information captured should be safely recovered and handed over to the stake-holders. Source code should be disposed only after determining the relevance of use in future or in a new software system that replaces the software system under retirement.

The resources include customized hardware, computers, devices etc. Efforts should be made to avoid disposing as this creates significant amount of e-Waste. If such hardware is inefficient or does not help in any way, these could be used in other software systems whose resource requirements are less or the organizations can make use of these resources for training and knowledge sharing or donate it to universities which hold

research interest, educational institutions for educational purposes.

III. INFRASTRUCTURE FOR GREEN SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT MODEL

Infrastructure also plays a major role in developing software in an environment friendly. This includes the meeting rooms, stationary, hardware, software, support for travel, specialized equipments, power etc.

Meeting Rooms could be designed in such a way that natural light could be used for lighting instead of power consuming lighting devices. Air-conditioners can be avoided by providing natural ventilation or replacing them with power friendly fans. This would not only reduce power consumption but also save the environment from toxic materials used in air-conditioning; however this cannot be applicable in places where the climatic conditions are extreme.

Travel may be involved in each of these phases and should be avoided as much as possible. Air-travel is general mode of travel for business meetings. Jet fuels usually damage the environment significantly, so planning for alternate modes of transport should be preferred. Travel can also be avoided by using modern communication tools that include telephone, real-time content sharing applications video streaming, mail communication etc.

Storage and maintenance of project artifacts, source code and product deliverables are standard activities in software organizations. These are generally stored in large data-centers which need a dedicated place with proper cooling. These data-centers not only consume large amount of power [10] but also need periodic maintenance. Peer-to-Peer storage [11] [12] or Distributed Storage [13] solutions can be a way to avoid use of dedicated data-centers. This will reduce the power consumption, cost of storage and maintenance.

Use of Paper can be avoided; information can be maintained in electronic format. Digital signing can be used if authorization is required. Any kind of design document, architecture document, flow diagrams, etc can be maintained in electronic format or using standardized tool which are specialized in achieving these kinds of tasks. Electronic scratch pads can be used in place of paper.

In the process of knowledge transfer or technological training, e-books related to the product or technology should be preferred over physical books as they reduce the use of paper significantly.

IV. QUALITY PROCESSES FOR GREEN SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT MODEL

There are number of quality processes and standards which focus on improving the quality software. Some of them include Capability Maturity Model (CMM) [14], Six Sigma [15], etc describe the best way of ensuring quality of the software. These

models focus on improving factors like productivity, reliability, customer satisfaction etc.

A step further would be to include some concepts that not only stress on quality but also sustainability. Concepts of sustainability include parameters for controlling power consumption by the software, reducing the size of the source code, measuring the impact of the software on human or the environment while using or developing the software system, adaptability to legacy hardware and new once.

Metrics for different parameters related to environ- friendliness of the software and its development process should

be standardized and included as an additional dimension to the existing models to ensure software quality and sustainability. This will result in a Software quality process that helps in building environment friendly software and an improved development process. Fig. 3 illustrates the consolidation of best practices in the various SDLC phases for green software development.

Fig. 3 The Green Software Development Life Cycle Model

V. CONCLUSION

This paper tries to suggest some practices that help in developing a software system in an environment friendly way. The ideas presented here, if practiced, helps in reducing power consumption, use of paper, pollution or fossil fuel consumption due to unnecessary travel etc. It also stresses on building adaptable software systems which try to use existing hardware. In this way the amount of e-Waste can be reduced gradually. This also reduces the added costs in the organization's software development process. The products developed in such a way are eco-friendly and hence adds value to the customer. These practices bring in some intangible benefits such as building a responsibility to protect the environment, supporting environment friendly measures as an initiative from the organization's side as well as the customer's side. Finally, it helps the organizations to plan and build environment friendly Software development centres, products, processes and technologies.

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